

CASE REPORT

Successful Slow Pathway Ablation via Femoral Vein in Case of Inferior Vena Cava Interruption

Halil Ibrahim Kokcu, MD*; Osman Can Yontar, MD; Enes Kaya, MD; Berkant Ozturk, MD

Summary

In this report, we describe a patient with inferior vena cava interruption who also suffered from supraventricular tachycardia. Accessing the right atria through the inferior vena cava in these patients can be challenging. We would like to share our experience with utilizing long sheaths in such cases.

Keywords: ablation; electrophysiological study; inferior vena cava interruption; long sheath; supraventricular tachycardia (SVT)

Correspondance*

Halil Ibrahim Kokcu, MD
halilkokcu314@gmail.com

Department of Cardiology, Samsun University,
Faculty of Medicine, Samsun, Turkey

Received: 16 November 2023

Accepted: 31 December 2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10674510

Although catheter ablation is typically performed through the femoral vein, complete or partial occlusions can hinder the procedure's success by making it challenging to stabilize the catheter or reach the ablation site. To address such challenges, alternative approaches such as the superior vena cava approach for right-sided arrhythmias and the retrograde aortic approach for left-sided arrhythmias are recognized methods. The patient has provided informed consent for the publication of this case report.

Case Report

A 64-year-old female patient was referred to our center due to frequent palpitation attacks. The patient underwent an electrophysiological study, during which two femoral sheaths were placed in the femoral vein. Attempting to access the coronary sinus diagnostic catheter into the right atria, we encountered difficulty as the catheter tip was bent and could not enter the right atrial chamber (Video 1). Venography revealed near-complete interruption of the vena cava (Video 2). Consequently, we opted to use a 0.035 hydrophilic guidewire to navigate through a small passage into the right atria. Two guidewires were introduced through the occluded segment into the right atria, followed by placement of two transeptal sheaths (PREFACE® Braided Guiding Sheath, Johnson & Johnson Medical NV/SA, USA) in the right atrial cavity over these wires (Video 3 and 4). Subsequently, a decapolar coronary sinus catheter and a diagnostic catheter were positioned in the coronary sinus and high right atrial position, respectively. Atrial decremental pacing demonstrated crossover and 1:2 response. Programmed stimulation induced supraventricular tachycardia with a VA interval of 50 msec. All other examinations supported the diagnosis of atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia. Interruption of ventricular overdrive pacing resulted in a V-A-V response, and His refractory premature ventricular single-beat stimulation did not advance or

reset retrograde A. Following the diagnosis, the diagnostic catheter was exchanged with an ablation catheter (Marinr MC ablation catheter, Medtronic, Minneapolis, MN, USA). Koch triangle was mapped with the ablation catheter to identify an appropriate location for radiofrequency application, and successful slow pathway ablation was performed.

Discussion

Atrioventricular nodal reentry is the most common form of paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia, and the primary therapeutic option for this type of arrhythmia is catheter ablation.¹ Both anatomical and electrical targets have been developed for ablation, which are situated within the Koch triangle.² Despite established techniques for the ablation procedure, anatomical obstacles can still pose challenges. These obstacles may include a narrow Koch triangle, a large coronary sinus ostium, or other factors that hinder catheter entrance into the right atrial chamber, as described in our case.

Interruption of the inferior vena cava (IVC) is a rare congenital venous anomaly often associated with heterotaxy syndromes. The prevalence of IVC interruption among patients undergoing routine imaging (computed tomography or echocardiography) ranges from 0.15% to 0.25%.³ Generally, if there is continuity via the azygos vein, procedures can be completed via femoral access. However, the most commonly utilized approach for these patients is through subclavian or jugular veins.⁴ Recently, there have been case reports describing procedures performed via hepatic vein access.⁵ Our case is unique among others described in the literature^{6,7} because of the interruption in the superior segment, nearly at the veno-right atrial junction.

Transthoracic echocardiography did not reveal any valve or embryonic remnants. In our case, we opted to utilize two long sheaths because the occluded segment was superior to the hepatic vein, and there was an opportunity to pass wires through the incompletely occluded segment, which fortunately we were able to achieve. Although we had limited maneuvering space, it proved to be sufficient for successful slow pathway ablation.

In conclusion, in cases of partial occlusions in the superior parts of the vena cava, catheter ablation with long sheaths is feasible. In such scenarios, utilizing the femoral vein route may be preferred over an unstable route like the superior vena cava.

You can access the videos mentioned in the article at the following address.

<https://jaejournalvideos.com.bilkentaritmi.com.tr/a2videos.html>

Conflict of Interests

None

Funding

The authors state that the current study received no financial support.

References

1. Forkman M, Schwab C, Busch S. Catheter ablation of supraventricular tachycardia. *Herzschrittmacherther Elektrophysiol.* 2019;30(4):336-342.
2. Jansen H, Nurnberg JH, Veltmann C, Hebe J. Anatomy for ablation of atrioventricular nodal reentry tachycardia and accessory pathways. *Herzschrittmacherther Elektrophysiol.* 2022;33(2):133-147.
3. Malaki M, Willis AP, Jones RG. Congenital anomalies of the inferior vena cava. *Clin Radiol.* 2012;67(2):165-171.
4. Martins RP, Behar N, Galand V, et al. Radiofrequency ablation of right ventricular tachycardia in patients with no femoral access: safety and efficacy of a superior approach. *Europace.* 2019;21(5):803-809.
5. Singh SM, Neuzil P, Skoka J, et al. Percutaneous transhepatic venous access for catheter ablation procedures in patients with interruption of the inferior vena cava. *Circ Arrhythm Electrophysiol.* 2011;4(2):235-241.

6. Kato H, Kubota S, Yamada Y, et al. Circumferential pulmonary vein ablation of atrial fibrillation via superior vena cava approach in a patient with interruption of the inferior vena cava. *Europace*. 2010;12(5):746-748.

7. Miyazaki S, Nault I, Haissaguerre M, Hocini M. Atrial fibrillation ablation by aortic retrograde approach using a magnetic navigation system. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol*. 2010;21(4):455-457.